

Evaluation of the Effect of Different Commercially Used Infectious Bursal Disease Vaccines in Nigeria on Haematological Parameters and Bursa of Fabricius of Broilers

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This study was aimed at investigating the impact of live infectious bursal disease (IBD) vaccines on haematological parameters and the Bursa of Fabricius (BF) of Cobb 500[®] broiler chickens. Fifty-day-old broiler chicks were raised for 25 days and divided into groups A, B, C, D, and E. Group A served as the negative control, while groups B, C, D, and E were vaccinated with four commercially available intermediate IBD vaccines: ORNIVUR Intermediate Plus[®], Bioveta[®], Indox Private Limited[®], Venkateshwara Hatcheries PVT[®], and Hester Biosciences Limited Mehsana[®], respectively. Vaccination was conducted on day 14 after maternally derived antibodies would have waned. Changes in haematological parameters and histopathological changes in the Bursa of Fabricius on days 14 and 10 post-vaccination were determined. There was a high white blood cells count ($p \leq 0.05$) in groups D and E. Histopathology showed increased lymphocyte proliferation in the lymphoid follicle, increased thickness of inters follicular connective tissue and bursal capsule with increase in severity in group D and E. The findings suggests intermediate infectious bursal disease vaccines from Venkateshwara Hatcheries PVT and Hester Biosciences Limited, Mehsana, were more invasive compared to the other tested vaccines and can be used in areas with very virulent IBD virus (vvIBDV).

Keywords: Broilers, Bursa of Fabricius, Haematological Parameters, intermediate Infectious Bursal Disease Vaccines.

INTRODUCTION

Infectious bursal disease (IBD) is a highly contagious acute viral infection affecting young chickens (Etteradossi and Saif, 2008). Infectious bursal disease virus (IBDV), belonging to serotype 1, is a significant immunosuppressive virus in chickens, with a tropism for the bursa of Fabricius. Severe lymphocyte depletion in bursal follicles can occur as a result of intense replication

(Qin and Zheng, 2017). Infection with IBDV can exacerbate disease caused by other pathogens and reduce the bird's ability to respond to vaccination. The virus affects both the humoral and cellular immune responses of chickens (Sharma *et al.*, 2000). Studies have shown that different IBDV strains may vary in their virulence, affecting their ability to replicate *in vivo* and induce humoral immunity. However, the relative abilities of these IBDV strains to stimulate cell-mediated responses and their relationship with virulence remains unknown (Rautenschlein *et al.*, 2003).

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The IBDV is in the environment despite strict hygiene measures, therefore, vaccination against IBD is considered a crucial strategy for protecting young birds during the first weeks of life (Etteradossi and Saif, 2008). The standard approach to control IBD in chicks is to hyperimmunize breeders with inactivated vaccines. While passive immunity provides good protection during the initial weeks of life, permanent protection against IBD requires the administration of live vaccines. IBD live vaccines are categorized as "mild," "intermediate," or "hot" based on their virulence levels. Mild vaccines are safe for specific pathogen-free chickens but may not be very effective against high levels of maternal antibodies or very virulent IBDV strains. Intermediate and hot vaccines are more effective in vaccination but these can lead to moderate to severe lesions in the bursa of fabricius (Ates *et al.*, 2022). Infectious bursal disease causes significant economic losses in poultry due to immunosuppression in subclinical cases (Jackwood and Sommer, 2010). In acute cases, it is associated with mortality, hemorrhages, and damage to the bursa (Jackwood *et al.*, 2009). IBDV is highly stable in the environment, and infected chickens can shed the virus in faeces for up to 16 days (Crespo *et al.*, 2016). Live vaccines are primarily used to prevent infection, but the emergence of variant or newer strains of the IBDV has been reported to lead to vaccination failures (Mohamed *et al.*, 2014). In this study, the effects of various commercial intermediate Infectious bursal disease vaccines on haematological parameters and histopathological changes in the bursa of Fabricius of broilers vaccinated with the vaccines were assessed.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study location

The study was conducted in Sokoto metropolis, which serves as the capital of Sokoto State, Nigeria. Geographically, the state is situated between latitudes 12°N and 13°58N and has an elevation of approximately 308 meters above sea level. Sokoto State is characterized by short-grass savannah vegetation in the south and thorn vegetation in the north. It shares its boundaries with Zamfara State to the east, the Niger Republic to the north, and Kebbi State to the west and southwest (Sokoto, 2001).

Experimental Chickens

A total of 50-day-old unvaccinated commercial broiler chicks COBB500[®] were sourced from a reputable commercial hatchery. The chicks were subsequently housed in the poultry unit of the Avian clinic, Veterinary Teaching Hospital, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto. To ensure uniform conditions throughout the study, the

birds were raised in separate disinfected rooms of comparable size, under the same light regimen. They were provided with commercial feed (specifically, Chikun[®] feed) and fresh water *ad libitum*.

Vaccines

Four commercial intermediate IBD vaccines; 1-Venkateshwara Hatcheries PVT, LTD. 2-ORNIVUR Intermediate Plus Vaccine Bioveta, Czech Republic. 3-Hester Biosciences Limited Mehsana, India, 4-Indox Private Limited, Siswala P.O RawalwasKhurd, Hissar, Haryana, India, were used in the study.

Experimental design

The birds were assigned into five treatment groups (A, B, C, D, E), with each consisting of 10 birds. Group A served as the negative control, while Groups B, C, D, and E were designated for Gumboro vaccination. In the control group, blood samples were collected from five birds, and three birds were sacrificed for postmortem examination on the 14th day of life. In groups B, C, D, and E, Gumboro vaccinations were administered through the drinking water route at the recommended doses of 10ml per bird. Vaccinations were conducted at 14th day of the birds' age, guided by the maternal antibody titers of the procured chicks. On the 24th week of age, blood samples were collected from five birds in each of the vaccinated groups, and three birds from each group were sacrificed for postmortem examinations.

Determination of Haematological Parameters

The haematological indices determined included: Packed cell volume (PCV), Red blood cell count (RBC), Mean corpuscular volume (MCV), Mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH),

Mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC), White blood cell count (WBC) and Differential leukocyte count (neutrophils, eosinophils, basophils, lymphocytes, and monocytes). The mean values and standard errors were calculated using statistical tools in Microsoft Excel. Additionally, the MCV, MCH, and MCHC values were calculated using the following equations:

$$\text{MCV (fl)} = (\text{Hematocrit (PCV) in \%} / \text{RBC count in millions per microliter}) \times 10$$

$$\text{MCH (pg)} = (\text{Hemoglobin concentration in g/dL} / \text{RBC count in millions per microliter}) \times 10$$

$$\text{MCHC (g/dL)} = (\text{Hemoglobin concentration in g/dL} / \text{Hematocrit (PCV) in \%}) \times 100$$

Clinical Pathological Examination

A total of 25 blood samples were collected from the wing veins of selected birds using 2 ml sterile syringes and dispensed into anti-coagulant (EDTA) sample bottles for

Table 1: Mean (\pm SEM) hematological parameters of birds across groups

Parameter	Treatment group				
	A	B	C	D	E
PCV (%)	26 \pm 0.50	27 \pm 0.58	27 \pm 0.70	28 \pm 0.20	28 \pm 0.40
Hb (μ L)	8.30 \pm 0.16	8.74 \pm 0.24	8.52 \pm 0.22	8.98 \pm 0.12	8.96 \pm 0.14
RBC $\times 10^6$ /L)	2.67 \pm 0.12	3.03 \pm 0.10	2.99 \pm 0.12	3.16 \pm 0.05	3.15 \pm 0.11
MCV (fL)	97.37 \pm 2.60	89.10 \pm 1.38	90.30 \pm 1.71	89.45 \pm 0.98	88.88 \pm 1.90
MCH (pgL)	31.08 \pm 0.97	28.84 \pm 0.39	28.49 \pm 0.64	28.41 \pm 0.29	28.44 \pm 0.63
MCHC (g/dl)	31.92 \pm 1.55	32.37 \pm 0.23	31.55 \pm 0.27	32.07 \pm 0.20	32.00 \pm 0.21
WBC($\times 10^4$ /L)	10.76 \pm 0.44	10.78 \pm 0.37	11.54 \pm 0.86	12.26 \pm 0.60	16.10 \pm 0.13
Heterophils (%)	28 \pm 0.86	39 \pm 0.37	58 \pm 0.81	55 \pm 0.89	47 \pm 2.31
Lymphocytes (%)	40 \pm 1.15	44 \pm 1.14	50 \pm 2.15	70 \pm 0.74	59 \pm 0.60
Eosinophils (%)	1 \pm 0.00	1 \pm 0.20	1 \pm 0.20	1 \pm 0.24	2 \pm 0.24
Monocytes (%)	1 \pm 0.24	1 \pm 0.31	1 \pm 0.24	1 \pm 0.24	1 \pm 0.20
Basophils (%)	0.00 \pm 0.00				
Band cells (%)	0.00 \pm 0.00				

Key: PCV=packed cell volume, Hb= hemoglobin, RBC= red blood cells, MCV= Mean corpuscular volume, MCH= mean corpuscular hemoglobin, MCHC= mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration, WBC= white blood cell count

Figure 1. Photomicrograph of group A showing normal bursa of fabricius architecture

Figure 2. Photomicrograph of group B showing increased lymphocytes and size of lymphoid follicles with thickness of bursal capsule

Figure 3. Photomicrograph of group C showing increased lymphocytes in the lymphoid follicles and increased thickness of interfollicular connective tissue and bursal capsule

Figure 4. Photomicrograph of group D showing severe increase in lymphocyte in the lymphoid follicle and increased thickness of interfollicular connective and bursal capsule

a complete blood count.

Histopathological Examination

The collected tissue samples from the BF were first fixed in 10% buffered formalin. Subsequently, they underwent histopathological preparation and examination, following the methods described by Sanofi *et al.* (2011).

Statistical Analysis

To assess differences in the number of birds or groups developing histological lesions, statistical analysis was conducted using one-way ANOVA (Analysis of Variance). The results obtained were then subjected to statistical comparison and evaluation using MS Excel. SPSS 21.0 version was used and values where P was less than 0.05 were considered to be statistically significant.

RESULTS

Changes in Haematological Parameters

Haematological results of five different groups of birds are presented in Table 1 below. The PCV and hemoglobin levels were not significantly influenced in this

study. However, a significant difference was observed in the mean RBC count ($p \leq 0.05$). Group D had the highest mean, while Group C had the lowest mean, which was higher than that of the unvaccinated group.

Vaccinated birds exhibited a significant increase in the proportion of WBCs in the leukogram ($p \leq 0.05$). Group B had the lowest WBC count, slightly above that of the unvaccinated group (A), while group E had the highest mean WBC counts among the groups. Additionally, vaccinated birds displayed a significant increase in the proportion of heterophils in the leukogram ($p \leq 0.05$). Group B had the lowest mean heterophils count, below that of the unvaccinated group, while C had the highest mean count among the vaccinated.

Furthermore, vaccinated birds showed a significant increase in the proportion of lymphocytes in the leukogram ($p \leq 0.05$). Group B had the lowest mean count, below that of the unvaccinated group, while Group D had the highest mean among the vaccinated groups. The proportions of monocytes and eosinophils in the leukogram were not significantly influenced in any of the groups ($p \leq 0.05$).

DISCUSSION

Infectious bursal disease virus is among the most

Figure 5. Photomicrograph of group E showing severe increase in lymphocyte in the lymphoid follicle and increased thickness of interfollicular connective and bursal capsule

important pathogens of poultry because it replicates and damages the tissues of the immune system (Dey *et al.*, 2019). The virus is ubiquitous in poultry production systems due to its unusually resistant physicochemical characteristics, combined with infrequent clean-out and disinfection of poultry houses (Etteradossi *et al.*, 2004). Although IBD vaccination is regularly practiced in poultry industry, the selection of more active types has occurred (Dey *et al.*, 2019).

This study presents the mean values of hematological parameters and histopathological changes in broiler birds vaccinated with Gumboro vaccines. The mean values of erythrocyte parameters, including hemoglobin, PCV, MCV, MCH, and MCHC in this study, are closely similar to values obtained in the work of Zeryehun *et al.* (2012). The mean of white blood cells is much higher than that reported in a similar work by Uko and Ataja (1996), and Zeryehun *et al.* (2012) in Nigeria and Malaysia respectively where it was mentioned that Infectious bursal disease virus has been reported to cause alterations in different haematological parameters of poultry. Normal histological appearance of follicle structure was observed in group A, which is the unvaccinated group. Group B exhibited increased lymphocytes, an increase in lymphoid follicular size, and increased thickness of the bursa capsule.

The histological appearance from group C shows increased lymphocytes in the lymphoid follicle, an increased thickness of interfollicular connective tissue, and bursal capsule. In group D, there is a severe increase in lymphocytes in the lymphoid follicle, increased thickness of interfollicular connective tissue, and bursal capsule. In group E, there is a severe increase in lymphocytes and the sizes of lymphoid follicles, with thickened interfollicular connective tissue and bursal capsule. Histopathological studies of lymphoid organs indicated vaccines induced bursal changes after vaccination as reported by Lukert and Saif (1997). All the vaccines provided protective immune responses. However, vaccines D and E appeared to be slightly more invasive compared to vaccines B and C.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, histopathological examination revealed increased levels of lymphocytes, lymphoid proliferation, increased thickness and size, and fibrous connective tissue proliferation in the vaccinated groups. Based on the findings, it can be inferred that the commercially available live infectious bursa disease vaccines in groups D and E exhibited a slightly greater invasiveness

compared to vaccines B and C. This conclusion is drawn from the observation that the bursal changes manifested more severely in groups receiving vaccines D and E.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Cleaning and disinfection are not always handled properly and, at times, may not be effective at eliminating highly resistant viruses such as IBDV, unless vaccination practices are substantially improved. In addition, inconsistencies in vaccine dosage, the indirect targeting of tissues that generate immunity, unequal distribution, and variability in water quality are common problems that accompany vaccination methods used in large-scale poultry operations.

Therefore, several parameters should be evaluated for the successful implementation of an infectious bursa disease virus vaccination program. However, further studies may be conducted to strengthen these observations

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